

Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction on TransJakarta Commuter System

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ABSTRACT: *One of the problems in big cities are transportation. They solve this problem by providing mass transportation such as bus or train. People use this facility to travel between surrounding cities or within the city. Jakarta recently has a new public transportation called TransJakarta which serving people traveling from nearby cities and in the city. In order to move or doing business between places people in Jakarta use TransJakarta. This research aims to analyse ticket price, service quality and customer value toward customer satisfaction. We conducted a research by using questionnaires given to the passengers and developed a model using a multiple regression to process the result from questionnaires. Samples were taken from The number of sample for this research was 130 customers taken from one bus stop which passengers traveled from BSD City to Grogol and Slipi. The results from partial testing showed that customer value and service quality have effect on customer satisfaction while ticket price does not have effect on customer satisfaction.*

Keywords: *TransJakarta, Ticket Price, Service Quality, Customer Value, Customer Satisfaction*

I. INTRODUCTION

Jakarta is one of the busiest city in the world. According to Jakarta's bureau of statistic the population in 2014 has reached 10.08 million people and human density is 15,234 per km². Jakarta is surrounded with cities of Bogor, Depok, Tangerang and Bekasi where they growth are also increased. This may due to the fast growing of Jakarta. People who commute into and around Jakarta are amounted to 3,566,178. This number consists of 2,429,751 people who is working or have education in Jakarta and the rest is having activities around Jakarta. People of Jakarta prefer to travel using their own transportation such as motorcycles and private cars. The number of people who traveling with personal transportation is very high which creates traffic jammed at every corner of the city. People need affordable mass transportation to support their activities. One of the solutions that already in place is public busses. There are many busses operate in Jakarta most of them are running by private business. Local government conducted public bus service called TransJakarta.

TransJakarta started its operation in 2016 with quiet short route about 20 kilometers, Kebayoran in South Jakarta to Kota in North Jakarta. The response to this facility was very highly acclaimed, people start to ride this bus to travel between buildings or utilize it as a transportation to go to the offices. The ticket price is very cheap and lower than private bus. Passangers pay only one price for one route.

Since the success introduction of TransJakarta, more busses and routes are applied. Many people using its services to carry them in doing the business. Bekasi, Bogor and Tangerang are also included in their services. Workers who have live in these surrounding areas and have their offices in Jakarta would prefer to use this transportation facility in order to avoid traffic jam.

There are more people using TransJakarta and the government who running the service also improve its facilities and service to meet customer expectation. Improvement has been done such as security, clean bus stop, member card and short ticketing queue. These improvements have been done in order to make customer experience a joyable ride.

II. THEORITICAL BACKGROUND AND HYPHOTESIS

According to Walton (2004) the price and quality has a high impact on customer satisfaction, however there is a little empirical evidence to explore this relationship. Number of Researcher supports the existence of the difference between the goal and the perceived price. Allen (2006) in his study shows that consumers do not always remember the actual price of a product. Instead, they encode the price in a way that is meaningful to them. Kotler (2005) mentioned that the

level of consumer attention, awareness and knowledge about the prices seemed much lower from consumers to know the accurate pricing of an internal reference for products.

Hyphotesis 1: Is ticket price has effect on customer satisfaction

According to the American Society for Quality Control, the overall quality traits and characteristics of a product or service in its ability to meet the needs that has been determined or can be latent or permanent Kotler (2005).

While Tjiptono (2004) suggests that the quality is a dynamic condition related to products, services, people, processes, and environments that meet or exceed expectations. Kotler (2005) states the service is any activity and the benefits that can be provided by one party to another party which is essentially intangible and does not have to result in the ownership. According to Parasuraman, et al. (2008), service quality can be defined as the extent to which the difference between reality and expectations of customers for the services they received or acquired. While Lovelock in Tjiptono (2004) states that service quality is the level of excellence expected from consumer and has control over the level of excellence to meet consumer desires.

Hyphotesis 2: Is service quality has effect on customer satisfaction

According Turel, et al. (2007) the basis of perceived value good value is to attract people who have the same perception about values, not just knowledge of the technology in general. A brand is the most superior among other brands will occupy the first position in the minds of consumers and the brands that are most easily remembered by consumers. This is very advantageous because if the consumer makes a purchase, the brand that has most memorable as the first time will be considered for selection. Rangkuti (2006) defines value as the overall assessment of the benefits of a product, customer perception is based on what has been received by customers and has been given by the product. The concept of customer value provides an overview of the customers of a company that is considering what they want and believe that they benefit from a product that they get Lapierre, (2000). The concept of customer value as a time of sacrifice has found one important element as a determinant of value and customer repurchase intention Kumar (2002).

Hyphotesis 3: Is customer value has effect on customer satisfaction

Understanding customer satisfaction is an essential element which reflects the success of manufacturers or service providers. The word satisfaction is derived from the Latin "satis" (means good enough, adequate) and "facio" (do or make), so that satisfaction may be interpreted as an "effort to fulfill something" or "make something adequate" (Tjiptono and Chandra, 2011). According to Lovelock et al. (2010), satisfaction ratings are a kind of behavior that occurred after consuming the service experience.

Conceptual Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was done at bus stop located in Grogol which is one of busiest bus stop of TransJakarta. Passengers who travel from BSD City to Grogol and Slipi will ride at this bus stop. In designing the research, we used associative causal design which useful to analyze the causal from independent variable to dependent variable. Independent variables were ticket price (X1), service quality (X2) and customer value (X3), whereas customer satisfaction (Y) was assigned as dependent variable. Questionnaire and literatures review were used in getting the data and related information. The questionnaires werespreaded to bus passangers and gathered to be processed by SPSS program to get statistic results.

Books findings were used to get the theory and additional information regarding the variables. There were 130 respondents used in analyzing the result. The research tests were validity, reliability, normality, multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, multiple linear regression and hypothesis test.

Questionnaires were distributed to 70 males and 60 females consists of 28.5 percent was age below 20, 36.2 percent was age between 20 to 25 and 35.4 percent was above 25 years old.

IV. ANALYSIS RESULT

Validity test is done by using the Pearson product moment correlation using SPSS 20. Ticket price, service quality and customer value, whereas customer satisfaction variables are analyzed and declared valid. Cronbach alpha test is used to measure the reliability test. It is found that Cronbach Alpha test results are 0.738, 0.788 and 0.612 respectively. The results were higher than 0.6 meaning that data is reliable.

Data normality test was carried out by P-plot and the result were points spread around the diagonal line and follow the direction of the diagonal line. It can be concluded that the data in this study are normally distributed.

Multicollinearity test was performed to determine whether or not there were collinearities between independent variables. Method used is to calculate Tolerance and VIF (Variance Inflation Factor). The test result showed at the table below:

Model	Tolerance	Cut Off	VIF	Cut Off
Ticket Price	0.241		4.146	
Service Quality	0.247	> 0.1	4.052	< 10
Customer Value	0.239		4.481	

The above table shows there are no sign of multicollinearities between variables tested.

Heteroscedasticity test in this research was done through a method by looking at the results of a data scatterplot. Data that has been residually standardized (Sdresid) with the results predicted dependent variable which has been standardized (Zpred). The result from scatter plot shows that there was no form a specific pattern of data. Points not only accumulate above or below the number 0 alone but spread above and below Y axis.

Multiple regression is an extension of simple linear regression. It is used when we want to predict the value of a variable based on the value of two or more other variables. The variable we want to predict is called the dependent variable (or sometimes, the outcome, target or criterion variable). The variables we are using to predict the value of the dependent variable are called the independent variables (or sometimes, the predictor, explanatory or regressor variables). Multiple regression is to determine the overall fit (variance explained) of the model and the relative contribution of each of the predictors to the total variance explained

Multiple Regression Table

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	247	1.006		248	.807
Ticket Price	.089	.067	.130	1.321	.189
Service Quality	.263	.042	.918	9.424	.000
Customer Value	-.209	.089	-.233	-2.353	.020

From the above table we created a multiple regression equation bellow:

$$Y = 247 + 0.89X1 + 0.394X2 - 0.209X3$$

Where

Y = Customer Satisfaction, X1 = Ticket Price, X2 = Service Quality and X3 = Customer Value

If there is an increase in ticket price and service quality there would be an increase in customer satisfaction, however if there is an increase customer value, the customer satisfaction would decrease.

T-statistical test indicates how far the influence of the independent variables individually in explaining variation of the dependent variable. It is to show that the independent variable has a significant effect or not. T-test was conducted to find out the effect of each independent variable (X) to dependent variable (Y). The result is compared with the value of t from t-table. T-test result showed that ticket price has value of 1.321 which is lower than 1.645 (t-table) meaning that ticket price does not have effect on customer satisfaction. Service quality and customer value have higher number than t-table. This shows that both independent variables have effect on customer satisfaction.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results and data processed, the following are the conclusions:

Ticket price does not an effect on customer satisfaction. Since this is a public transportation provided by the government the ticket price is already lower than regular transportation served by private. Government is willing to subsidise this

program due to providing low price public transportation. This may be the reason why the ticket price did not have effect on customer satisfaction.

Service quality and customer value have effect on customer satisfaction these are in line with research done by Marchall (2015). It is obvious that customer or riders expect high quality service and customer value when utilize services provided by Trans Jakarta. Further suggestion might be useful if operator can provide a better service and give higher value to customers to gain satisfactory factor from customers.

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